

LONG-TERM DEMAND IMPACTS OF ENHANCED GROUND ACCESS TO A SECONDARY AIRPORT WITH LOW COST CARRIER OPERATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims at simulating the long-term demand impacts of improving ground access to a secondary airport with low cost carrier operations in a multiple airport region. We analyze the São Paulo multi airport system – Guarulhos, Congonhas and Viracopos – under a high-speed railway (TAV) scenario. We develop a model of air travel demand forecasts for the São Paulo metropolitan region and generate traffic splits between the existing airports using a conditional logit model with access time as a key variable. Results show that an enhanced ground access would increase Viracopos' demand by 26% to 34%.

Keywords: secondary airport, low cost carrier, demand forecast, ground access, conditional logit.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper aims at assessing the impact of introducing a high speed railway linking Rio de Janeiro and São Paulo states in Brazil on the air travel demand for the São Paulo Metropolitan Region airports. This new system is currently under public debate and is planned not only to provide an alternative mean of transportation between the two major cities of the Southwest of the country but also to enhance the accessibility to the rapidly-growing secondary Campinas-Viracopos Airport (VCP). VCP is 60 miles distant from São Paulo city downtown and its current low cost flights operations would be notably benefitted from enhanced accessibility to the zones of highest air travel generation. We develop a model of air travel demand forecasts for the São Paulo metropolitan region and generate traffic splits between the existing airports by using a conditional logit model with access time as a key variable. For the airport-specific demand forecasts we consider the scenarios with and without an operating high-speed rail system.

Besides VCP, air travel demand in the São Paulo region is currently served by two major airports, namely São Paulo-Guarulhos International (GRU) and São Paulo-Congonhas (CGH). GRU is the largest airport and serves as a major national and international hub. In 2008 the airport had two terminals, but its master plan demanded two additional terminals and possibly another runway, allowing the airport to serve up to 45 million passengers yearly (McKinsey, 2009). CGH is the downtown airport, being the second largest airport of the region, with shuttle flights between São Paulo and Rio de Janeiro, the densest Brazilian route. While conveniently located close to the city center, this airport was severely limited regarding expansion capabilities and was not expected to accommodate more than 15 million passengers yearly (McKinsey, 2009). VCP was intended, as of its inception, to become the major airport for São Paulo, and its master plan foresaw a yearly demand of 60 million passengers. However, this airport is considerably far from the city center with access times from São Paulo downtown reaching more than two hours. Current available access mode is only via car and bus. Despite its location disadvantage, the air travel demand in

VCP has considerably grown since 2009 due to the entry of the low cost carrier Azul Airlines. VCP is currently the main hub for the LCC. Important to note that a "hub" may be a concept related to either the airport point of view (e.g., GRU) or the airline point of view (e.g., Azul at VCP). Costa, Lohmann and Oliveira (2010; 2011) discuss that it is the concentration of traffic in both space and time, along with centrality, that define a hub. Although these are the criteria for our preferred concept of hub, we are aware that a colloquial usage of the term is frequently associated with "airports that handle large volumes of traffic (...)" (Holloway, 2008, p. 376).

In the meantime the government continued to push for the introduction of a high speed railway between Rio de Janeiro and São Paulo. Figure 1 presents the proposed route for the high-speed train. In this context, the McKinsey & Company airport study (McKinsey, 2009) advised the government to expand VCP to its planned capacity, precluding the existing alternative approach of building a new airport in the São Paulo Metropolitan Region. However, the demand forecasts of McKinsey (2009) were considerably conservative. For example, the 2011 traffic was 96.4% of the 2014 aggressive forecast of that study, with several cities already exceeding expected 2014 values.

The current paper's main goal is to recalculate the demand forecasts of McKinsey (2009), taking into account the scenario of the availability of an operating high-speed train and its potential impact on access time to VCP. Therefore, we perform a revision of existing forecasts by employing a procedure that takes into account income inequality for GDP adjustment, as proposed by Sen (1982). Indeed, Brazil has recently experienced a remarkable reduction in income inequality coupled with relatively high GDP growth (Soares, 2008 and Barros et. al. 2010). Adjusting for income inequality is a procedure that at the same time enhances the realism of the hypotheses of the econometric model performed by McKinsey (2009) and permits more adequate demand forecasts. Finally, a discrete choice model is developed for the VCP, GRU and CGH airports based on a conditional logit model. This model

is integrated to the demand forecast and used to generate traffic splits by airport for 2030.

This paper is organized in the following way. In the second section, an analysis of the literature of air transportation demand in regions with multiple airports is performed. In the third section, we present a discussion of the demand forecasts of McKinsey (2009) and develop reviewed forecasts using the proposal of Sen (1982). In the fourth section, we present our conditional logit model for estimating traffic split estimation for the São Paulo area airports considering changes in access time. In the fifth section, we perform demand estimation for the São Paulo area airports considering changes in access time and the impact of the high-speed train on forecasted demand. Final conclusions are then presented in the final section.

2. AIR TRANSPORTATION DEMAND IN REGIONS WITH MULTIPLE AIRPORTS

Most research on airport choice models refers to Skinner (1976) as the first relevant attempt to model the choice behavior of passenger on multi-airport systems. In this study the author considered the three airports in the Washington-Baltimore area: Washington National, Baltimore-Washington International and Washington Dulles International using a multinomial logit model.

Skinner (1976) employed a revealed preference approach, with two sets of regressors: variables related to flight frequency at the chosen airport and variables related the ease of access to the airport. Regarding frequency, two direct flight frequency variables were used: one based on the number of weekday flights for the passenger's destination and another based on the number of weekday flights for the passenger's destination and period of choice. The automobile access time and access utility were used as access variables. Passengers were segmented into business and non-business groups, under an assumption that these groups might have different choice behaviors. Although 16,000 interviews were conducted, only 1,552 questionnaires were actually used. Skinner (1976) concluded that all variables had statistical significance, in other words, they were relevant for choice. He also concluded that

business travelers were more sensitive to accessibility and less sensitive to flight frequency. It is worth noting his conclusion that only large changes in frequency were capable of significantly changing airport choice.

Harvey (1987) studied the San Francisco Bay Area using a multinomial logit model. The San Francisco Bay Area is served by three airports: San Francisco International (SFO), Oakland International (OAK) and San Jose Municipal (SJC). The author also adopted a revealed preference approach, using 2,800 questionnaires, of which 1,860 were valid. Similarly to Skinner (1976), access and frequency variables were employed. The access variable used was access time and the frequency variables used were the number of frequencies to the chosen destination, considering connections, and the number of direct frequencies to the chosen destination. The author concluded that direct flights have greater probability of choice than flights with connection, that frequencies, after a certain level, seem to reach a cap in their attractiveness ability, that the choice of access mode does not impact airport choice, that very high access times have a lower negative impact on attractiveness and that shorter flights were more time-sensitive.

Windle and Dresner (1995) also analyzed the Baltimore-Washington area using a multinomial logit model with a revealed preference approach. The authors segmented passengers into four groups: 948 residents travelling on business, 546 other residents, 1,947 non-residents travelling on business and 1,041 other non-residents. The authors used access time and weekly flight frequencies to each chosen destination as variables. However, they added a third type of variable related to experience with the airport. The authors ultimately reinforced the conclusion of Skinner (1976): business travelers were more time-sensitive. They also found that these passengers have increased sensitivity to frequency. Furthermore, they found out that experience was a very significant variable for choice, demonstrating the relevance of considering this factor in airport choice studies.

Finally, Pels, Nijkamp and Rietveld (1998) also studied airport choice in the San Francisco Bay Area, adding the Sonoma County

airport to the three airports analyzed by Harvey (1987). They considered 21,459 passengers in a revealed-preference approach and also segmented passengers into business and non-business categories. 5,016 business questionnaires were effectively used and 6,249 other questionnaires were used. Instead of using a multinomial logit approach, they employed a nested logit approach. The authors used flight frequency, access time, number of seats per flight and air fares for each passenger as regressors and concluded that airport choice precedes air carrier choice. They also concluded that seasonality considerably affected variable behavior. Furthermore, they observed that business and non-business passengers had similar behaviors when seasonality was taken into account.

3. DEFINITION OF DEMAND BASELINE FOR AIRPORTS IN THE SÃO PAULO AREA

3.1. Demand Forecasts according to McKinsey (2009)

McKinsey (2009) developed two models in order to forecast air passenger demand for Brazilian airports, one of them using a bottom-up approach and another using a top-down approach. The bottom-up model estimates demand for individual airports separately based on existing routes. National demand is considered to be the sum of these forecasts. The top-down model estimates national demand first and then uses estimates of airport traffic share for an interval of years to generate forecasts for each airport. The bottom-up model is better suited to model particularities of each airport, but does not account either for new routes or changes in competitive relationships between airports, unlike the top-down model. Therefore, the top-down model is better suited for long-term forecasts whereas the bottom-up methodology is precise for a short span of time. As this study is concerned with long-term implications for VCP all subsequent analysis is based on the top-down model.

McKinsey (2009) used data from 1979 up to 2008 to estimate demand for the years between 2010 and 2030. 2009 was extrapolated from partial yearly results and incorporated into

the series. The logarithmic regression model used national and global GDP as well as national and international yield values as explanatory variables. Additionally, a dummy variable was included accounting for the effects of the deregulation of the Brazilian air transportation market in 2002.

The model above described was estimated by McKinsey, obtaining the coefficients for the explanatory variables. Using these values as well as the market share forecast, McKinsey developed airport-specific forecasts for each year between 2010 and 2030. A way to test the model's effectiveness is to check whether the forecast air passenger traffic numbers match actual numbers already available. These numbers were obtained from Infraero, which has data for 2010 and 2011.

Table 1 compares forecasted and actual numbers, considering the more optimistic estimation performed by McKinsey (2009). As Table 1 shows, the error was above 15% in 2010 and surpassed 20% in 2011, possibly indicating a systematic downward bias. This bias, if true, accumulates over the forecast years, with severe implications for forecast quality by 2030. Given the size of the bias it is important either to adjust the model or employ an alternate forecast.

3.2. Adjustment of McKinsey model to actual results

Even though the forecasts developed by McKinsey (2009) proved to be considerably conservative we considered using them as a basis for discussion if the error sources are understood and are eliminated or mitigated. Four sources of error were identified. The first is the use of estimated, instead of actual, air passenger traffic statistics as the last year of the historical series, 2009. We observed that the numbers were systematically underestimated, amounting to a total 3.3% lower than the actual. A second source of error is the divergence between forecast GDP and yield values and actual values. A third possible source of error would be a change in the way the explanatory regression variables behave. The logarithmic regression model supposes that the relationship between demand and the logarithm of each explanatory variable is constant. As the series

used goes back to 1979 it is reasonable to question whether the relationships for the more recent years and for the forecast future years are different from those at the beginning of the series. This might not be obvious in the model, as changes in a few years at the end of the series might not severely decrease the R^2 value. A fourth source of error can possibly be the neglect of significant explanatory variables. This might involve not just the neglect of a variable relevant to the entire series, but also of a variable relevant only for the final years. Similarly to the above explained, this might not severely decrease R^2 . This also might not be manifest in p-values and other measures of significance.

An important factor of structural change in the last few years not considered by McKinsey (2009) was the remarkable reduction in income inequality in Brazil, coupled with relatively high GDP growth (Soares, 2008 and Barros et. al., 2010). According to studies such as Neri (2008), this has led to the consolidation of a new group of consumers dubbed as “The New Middle Class”. It is fair to assume that this has a potential impact on the demand for air travel in the country.

Based on the four hypothesis, three adjustments were made: use of actual 2009 figures as a starting point for forecast; adjustment of forecasts for explanatory variables and a correction of the projected GDP series to reflect income inequality. Income inequality was incorporated into the model using a GDP adjustment proposed by Sen (1982). This is expressed by equation 1:

$$S = \mu(1 - G) \quad (1)$$

In equation 1, S is the adjusted income, μ is the unadjusted income and G is the Gini inequality index. Gini index data were obtained from IPEA (Soares, 2008) and extrapolated for the subsequent years.

Table 2 shows the reviewed forecasts considering all adjustments.

It is possible to observe that the impact from 2009 data was small and that GDP, yield and inequality adjustments were very meaningful. Table 3 compares the forecasts performed by McKinsey (2009), the adjusted forecasts and the actual numbers. We observed

that the reviewed forecasts considerably reduced errors, even though they did not achieve a perfect match.

3.3. Definition of final demand baseline for São Paulo area

The adjusted McKinsey model makes it possible to define a new demand baseline for the São Paulo area. Considering market shares forecasted by McKinsey (2009), the values on Table 3 are obtained for the aggregate demand of the São Paulo area. This demand forecast will be called from now on the neutral baseline. Table 4 indicates that the airports will exceed their maximum capacity of about 165 million passengers by 2030, already taking into account foreseen infrastructure improvements.

Our neutral baseline may be considered too optimistic for some reasons. The first is that it assumes that income inequality will keep decreasing over time at a rate of 0.006 Gini points per year. A study performed by IPEA (2007) indicates both that this is a high level of inequality reduction, compared to international benchmarks, and that Brazil had not experienced, until the current cycle, a period of decrease in income inequality longer than seven years since the Gini index began to be calculated. The second is a criticism to decreases in yield. It is possible that, as yields fell considerably in 2009, 2010 and 2011, much of the potential for yield reduction is spent. The third is the use of two high-growth years to test the effectiveness of the adjusted model. These high growth years might prove themselves to be exceptions to the model and therefore poor guides for evaluating its effectiveness. For these reasons, it is interesting to consider a more pessimistic scenario for forecasts in all analyses. A possibility would be to use McKinsey (2009)’s average scenario as a forecast. However, such a scenario would probably be too pessimist, in the light of recent data discussed by this study. A compromise can be achieved by averaging the two scenarios – which was performed and treated as a “conservative scenario”.

4. MODELING AIRPORT CHOICE IN THE SÃO PAULO AREA

With a demand baseline established, the second step of this study was to develop an airport choice model for the São Paulo Area. We used a conditional logit framework.

4.1. Description of data for modeling

Our dataset consists of a survey with air passengers at key Brazilian airports in 2009. This survey was carried out by Foundation Institute of Economic Research (FIPE, 2009). The survey set out to determine the cities which comprised the catchment area of each airport, the passenger's profiles and the routes that were chosen. Of particular interest to this study, the survey collected data on access modes, income, door-to-door airport access time and passenger origin (neighborhood level). A total of 9,200 observations were used for GRU, CGH and VCP, as shown in Table 5.

As discussed in the literature review, frequency variables are of capital importance for airport choice models. Frequency data was extracted from the HOTRAN – a daily compilation of registered flights at each airport performed by the Brazilian National Civil Aviation Authority. We used weekly (direct) frequencies as the frequency parameter.

Another important variable is access time. The survey of FIPE (2009) included data on time spent by each passenger to reach the airport. However, it is also important to know the access time to the airports not chosen. In order to do this, passengers were segmented into geographical zones. Eight of these zones were divisions within the São Paulo municipality (Figure 2 - A), three were divisions within the outer São Paulo Metropolitan Area (Figure 2 - B) and the two last ones were the Campinas Metropolitan Zone and the remnant of the São Paulo State (Figure 2 - C).

A third key attribute of passengers is experience with each airport. The survey of FIPE (2009) includes a question on the number of times an air route was taken by a passenger in the previous 12 months. This can be regarded as an indicator of the passenger previous experience with the airport. However, there is no ready information regarding experience with

other airports. Therefore it is necessary to estimate these parameters from the database. In order to do this, a three-step approach was adopted. First, the average experience of passengers at each zone was calculated. Based on this data, the next step was calculating for each passenger an *experience coefficient*. The experience coefficient denotes how much the passenger is experienced with an airport compared to peers in his region, and is given by Equation (2):

$$\text{experience coefficient} = \frac{\text{passenger experience}}{\text{average zone experience with airport}} \quad (2)$$

The final step assumes that the more experienced a passenger is with his airport of choice, the more experienced he is with the other airports. Based on this, the final operation is multiplying the experience coefficient by the average experience of zone peers with the non-chosen airports, thus yielding an estimate of passenger experience for the airports not chosen.

4.2. Description of models tested

Our choice model consists of a multinomial logit model, using frequency, experience and access time as regressors. The model variables are:

- Access Time (given in minutes)
- Weekly Direct Frequencies
- Number of times the route was taken in the last 12 months

Another aspect to be considered in the model definition is segmentation, a problem for which there is an important trade-off that must be taken into account. Different segments have different choice behaviors. Literature review suggests two divisions. The first is a division between business and non-business passengers. **Erro! Fonte de referência não encontrada.**6 shows how these two groups of passengers chose airports. It is possible to observe that business passengers tend to prefer CGH as opposed to GRU. This is natural since CGH is the closest airport to the business center.

However, this segmentation seems to have a limited effect on VCP.

The second is a division along regional or place of residence lines. Table 7 shows the choice split between the two regional segments. However, the decision of splitting into segments depends on the second element of the trade-off: the number of observations. A low number of observations affects the effectiveness of the model. In this study, in spite of the good number of observations, very few passengers chose VCP, only 436 out of 9,200. Moreover, several regions are underrepresented in this universe and excessive segmentation might mean that their behavior is altogether lost. Considering this trade-off, only one segmentation was used – the regional segmentation. This decision is justified by the greater interest that changes in access time to VCP, among all factors, offer to this study.

Therefore, there are two models to be initially fitted:

- A multinomial logit model with frequency, experience and access time variables for the São Paulo and Campinas metropolitan areas
- A multinomial logit model with frequency, experience and access time variables for municipalities in the São Paulo state outside the São Paulo and Campinas metropolitan areas

4.3. Models based on frequency, experience and access

One of the ways to verify the usefulness of a conditional logit is to calculate McFadden's R-squared. This metric depends both on the model tested and on a version of the model with no explanatory variables – the intercept model. In the intercept model, the intercept coefficient attempts to approximate the effect of all variables that could influence choice, but were not specified. Therefore, intercept models were estimated for the two regional segments. With intercept models estimated as comparison, the next step was to estimate models with the explanatory variables proposed.

4.3.1. Model for the São Paulo and Campinas Metropolitan Areas

Table 8 shows the results of fitting the conditional logit model with experience, access time and frequency variables to the first regional dataset, using GRU as base choice. The coefficients given are the confidants applicable to GRU and VCP when their choice probabilities are compared to the choice probability for CGH. Each choice has its own intercept. The coefficients for the experience, access time and frequency work in a different manner. The coefficients are global but each choice has its own variable for each of the three factors. The logarithm of the likelihood function equals -4503.0339. This, coupled with the likelihood from the intercept model, makes it possible to compute McFadden's R^2 . The 0.2983 value for McFadden's R^2 suggests a fair, though not excellent, fit. As expected, longer access times have a significant negative factor on choice, while higher frequencies encourage airport use. The $p > |z|$ test shows that the coefficients for these factors are not null, as well as the intercepts. However, the experience variable was not significant at the 95% or even at the 90% level, meaning that it offers no reliability for estimation. This makes it necessary to fit a model without the experience variable.

4.3.2. Model for the São Paulo State outside the São Paulo and Campinas Metropolitan Areas

Table 9 shows the results of fitting the conditional logit model with experience, access time and frequency variables to the second dataset, using GRU as base choice. The coefficients work in the same manner as in the previous model – constants for each choice and global coefficients for choice-specific variables. The 0.1044 value for McFadden's R^2 is a low value. This indicates that important factor not included in the model could improve it. Higher frequencies encourage airport use, with the frequency variable being significant to under the 1% level, as the $p > |z|$ test shows. The coefficients are significant as well. The experience and access variables were not significant. This makes it necessary to fit a

model without the experience and access variables.

4.4. Models based on frequency and access

Table 10 shows the results of fitting the conditional logit model with access time and frequency variables to the first dataset, using GRU as base choice. The 0.2932 value for McFadden's R^2 suggests that the frequency and access time model has a fair fit with data. As expected, longer access times have a significant negative factor on choice, while higher frequencies encourage airport use. The $p > |z|$ test shows that the coefficients for these factors are not null, as well as the intercepts. This indicates that this is a feasible model for airport choice in the São Paulo and Campinas Metropolitan Areas.

4.5. Models based on frequency

Table 11 shows the results of fitting the conditional logit model with frequency variables to the second regional dataset, using GRU as base choice. The 0.0978 value for McFadden's R^2 suggests that the frequency model has a limited descriptive power. As expected, higher frequencies encourage airport use. The $p > |z|$ test shows that the coefficient for frequency is not null, as well as the intercepts. Even though the model has a poor fit, it offers the important insights that access times are of little relevance for passengers outside São Paulo and Campinas and that frequency is still an important factor for choice. This will be important for the final demand estimation.

5. DEMAND ESTIMATION FOR THE SÃO PAULO AREA AIRPORTS CONSIDERING AIRPORT GROUND ACCESS ENHANCEMENT

With models both for the aggregate air travel demand and for airport choice within the São Paulo Metropolitan Region, it is possible to simulate the impact of access time on demand. This section discusses two scenarios for 2030: one that considers unchanged access times (baseline case) and another that considers reduced airport access times to VCP as

consequence of the introduction of the high-speed train.

5.1. Assumptions for passenger traffic in São Paulo in 2030

Before discussing the forecasting scenarios themselves, it is necessary to define common assumptions regarding the relationship between departures from the São Paulo state from VCP, CGH and GRU, which were modeled by this study, and overall passenger traffic at the airports. The first assumption is that departures from the São Paulo state can be considered equal to departures during a 12 month period. A second assumption is that any passenger originating outside the São Paulo state flies into the airport and therefore can be considered passenger in connection. This is supported by the fact that approximately 2% of passengers at the São Paulo airports who were not connection passengers originated outside the São Paulo State. A third assumption is related to the demand split within the São Paulo and Campinas metropolitan areas. Considering the demand growth forecast for the São Paulo state (McKinsey, 2009) and a benchmark share of connection flights, this study will use the shares shown in Table 12. This table shows the split between connections, flights originating from the São Paulo and Campinas Metropolitan Areas and flights from other parts of the São Paulo state. Passenger totals use the aggregate demand baseline given by the adjusted McKinsey (2009) estimates.

Based on these assumptions, the approach for estimating demand was: 1. Defining assumptions for frequency and accessibility for CGH, GRU and VCP in 2030; 2. Based on the final demand choice models, predict probabilities of choice for a forecasted "average profile" passenger; and 3. Multiply probabilities of choice by expected demand for segment, taking into account assumptions about demand split. Estimates were performed considering the neutral and conservative aggregate demand estimates.

5.2. Reference scenario – demand without changes in access time

The first scenario considers estimates of demand without the availability of a high-speed train. Its main assumptions are: 1. Frequencies at CGH are constant from 2008 due to capacity constraints; 2. The sum of frequencies for the three airports grows in tandem with the aggregate demand forecast; 3. Both domestic and international frequencies at GRU and CGH are proportional to maximum capacity (50 million and 80 million pax/year, respectively); 4. International and Domestic split is 10%; and 5. Access times are constant compared to 2008 for all airports. In this scenario, the forecast demand for each airport in 2030 is shown in Table 13 for the neutral baseline and in Table 14 for the conservative baseline.

5.3. Demand with the availability of high-speed train access to VCP

For the scenario with high-speed train availability, the assumptions were the same as those for the reference scenario, with a change in the access time to VCP, which is reduced to 55 minutes. In this scenario, the forecasted demand for each airport in 2030 is shown in **Erro! Fonte de referência não encontrada.**5 for the neutral baseline and in Table 16 for the conservative baseline.

The scenario with high-speed train availability forecasts an increase between 16.6 and 26.6 million passengers due to the high-speed train, which is an increase of 26% to 34% in total VCP airport movement. Without the high-speed train, GRU is nearly at full utilization (60 million passengers, as shown above) in the conservative scenario and far above it in the neutral scenario. On the other hand, VCP has some expansion potential left even in the more aggressive scenario. In the scenarios with high-speed train, using both the neutral and conservative baselines, GRU has demand below maximum capacity. In the conservative demand forecast, VCP is under full capacity, but over in the neutral demand forecasts.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper aimed at assessing the effects of changes in the access time to an important secondary airport in Brazil, Campinas-Viracopos airport (VCP), which belongs to the São Paulo Metropolitan Region in the Southeast of Brazil. Our focus is on the proposed introduction of a high-speed train Campinas-São Paulo-Rio de Janeiro, which would considerably enhance ground accessibility to VCP. An adjustment to official air travel demand forecasts was performed by employing an income-inequality adjustment in order to generate aggregate forecasts for the São Paulo region. A choice model between the three metropolitan airports was estimated using a conditional logistic regression. We found out that adjustments were capable of significantly improving the model's predictive power and substantially reducing forecast errors occurred in the first years after the forecast.

With the demand and choice models, a demand forecast was performed for 2030 for each of the three São Paulo area airports. We found out that the high-speed train could have a considerable influence on VCP's demand and therefore on the demand for the low cost carrier flights currently available at the airport. We could also observe that there is the possibility that all metropolitan airports achieve a demand level that exceeds capacity, concluding that a new airport would have to be built within the São Paulo Metropolitan Region before 2030.

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Figure 1: Proposed high-speed train route

Figure 2: Geographical Zones

Table 1: Comparison of optimistic forecasts and actual statistics for passenger traffic in the main Brazilian airports

Year	Forecast	Actual	Error (%)
2010	119,259,811	140,725,886	-15.30%
2011	127,556,413	161,151,773	-20.80%

Table 2: Comparison of baseline and different adjusted forecasts

	2030 Estimate (millions)	Difference from baseline (%)
Baseline scenario	308.4	-
With 2009 data	322.4	4.6%
Actual data + inequality adjustment	458.9	48.80%
Actual data + inequality adjustment + GDP adjustment	542.4	75.80%
Actual data + inequality adjustment + GDP adjustment + Yield adjustment	595	92.30%

Table 3: Comparison of forecasts for air passenger demand from McKinsey, reviewed forecasts and actual figures

Year	McKinsey	Reviewed forecast	Actual	Error - McKinsey (%)	Error - Reviewed (%)
2010	119,259,811	135,107,900	140,725,886	-15.3%	-4.0%
2011	127,556,413	147,789,993	161,151,773	-20.8%	-8.3%

Table 4: Aggregate demand for the São Paulo Area airports – Neutral baseline

Year	National Demand	São Paulo Domestic Share	São Paulo International Share	São Paulo Total Share	São Paulo Aggregate Demand
2014	194,599,845	28.34%	62.78%	31.79%	61,870,009
2020	295,190,443	36.91%	62.78%	30.51%	90,049,474
2030	594,996,829	24.43%	62.78%	28.24%	168,074,224

Table 5: Observations in data sample

Airport	Observations (absolute)	Observations (relative)
GRU	4,657	50.62%
CGH	4,107	44.64%
VCP	436	4.74%
Total	9,200	100.00%

Table 6: Passenger choice segment by travel purpose

Zone	Airport Choice			Total
	GRU	CGH	VCP	
Non-business	2952	1234	198	4024
Business	2065	2873	238	5176
Total	4657	4107	436	9200

Table 7: Choice split between passenger originating from São Paulo and Campinas metropolitan areas and from other São Paulo state municipalities

Zone	Airport Choice			Total
	GRU	CGH	VCP	
Metropolitan	3728	3851	267	7846
Non-Metropolitan	929	256	169	1354

Total	4657	4107	436	9200
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Table 8: Coefficients and standard deviations of frequency experience and access time model for the São Paulo and Campinas metropolitan areas

Airport Choice	Coefficients	Value (Standard Error)		P> z
GRU	----- Base Alternative -----			
CGH	Constant	-0.1367772 (0.0371713)	***	0.000
VCP	Constant	-1.603345 (0.071713)	***	0.000
All Choices	Experience	0.0005554 (0.0017613)		0.753
	Access Time	-0.0187811 (0.0007467)	***	0.000
	Direct Frequencies	0.0123996 (0.0004629)	***	0.000
Log-likelihood	-4503.0339			
Note: * = significantly different from zero at 10% level; ** = significantly different from zero at 5% level; *** = significantly different from zero at 1% level				

Table 9: Coefficients and standard deviations of frequency experience and access time model outside the São Paulo and Campinas metropolitan areas

Airport Choice	Coefficients	Value (Standard Error)		P> z
GRU	----- Base Alternative -----			
CGH	Constant	-0.7871112 (0.0963657)	***	0.000
VCP	Constant	-1.179225 (0.1082505)	***	0.000
All Choices	Experience	0.0085032 (0.0065405)		0.194
	Access Time	-0.0004319 (0.0006426)	***	0.502
	Direct Frequencies	0.0050551 (0.0013076)	***	0.000
Log-likelihood	-1010.3285			
Note: * = significantly different from zero at 10% level; ** = significantly different from zero at 5% level; *** = significantly different from zero at 1% level				

Table 10: Coefficients and standard deviations of frequency model for the São Paulo and Campinas metropolitan areas

Airport Choice	Coefficients	Value (Standard Error)		P> z
GRU	----- Base Alternative -----			
CGH	Constant	0.1383462 (0.0354405)	***	0.000
VCP	Constant	-1.588958 (0.071186)	***	0.000
All Choices	Access Time	-0.0189314 (0.0007398)	***	0.000
	Direct Frequencies	0.0123278 (0.0004594)	***	0.000
Log-likelihood	-4535.9802			
Note: * = significantly different from zero at 10% level; ** = significantly different from zero at 5% level; *** = significantly different from zero at 1% level				

Table 11: Coefficients and standard deviations of frequency model outside the São Paulo and Campinas metropolitan areas

Airport Choice	Coefficients	Value (Standard Error)		P> z
GRU	----- Base Alternative -----			
CGH	Constant	-0.8266825 (0.0012992)	***	0.000
VCP	Constant	-1.183999 (0.103355)	***	0.000
All Choices	Direct Frequencies	0.0049873 (0.0012992)	***	0.000
Log-likelihood	-1017.7736			
Note: * = significantly different from zero at 10% level; ** = significantly different from zero at 5% level; *** = significantly different from zero at 1% level				

Table 12: Assumptions for demand sources at the São Paulo Area airports for 2030

	Connection	São Paulo + Campinas Areas	Other São Paulo State	Total
Split	33,3%	50%	16.7%	100.0%
Neutral baseline (millions of passengers)	56.0	84.0	28.0	145.4

Conservative baseline (millions of passengers)	42.9	64.4	21.4	128.7
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Table 13: Demand for São Paulo Area airports in 2030 in a constant access time scenario, considering neutral baseline

Zone		VCP	GRU	CGH	Total
São Paulo and Campinas Metro (Dept+Arr)	Split	53.60%	42.80%	3.60%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	45	35.9	3.1	84
Other São Paulo state (Dept+Arr)	Split	35.10%	55.80%	9.10%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	9.8	15.6	2.5	28
Connections	Split	48.90%	46.10%	5.00%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	27.7	25.8	2.7	56
Total	Split	48.90%	16,7%	50%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	77.4	82.2	8.3	168.1

Table 14: Demand for São Paulo Area airports in 2030 in a constant access time scenario, considering the conservative baseline

Zone		VCP	GRU	CGH	Total
São Paulo and Campinas Metro (Dept+Arr)	Split	53.60%	42.80%	3.60%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	34.5	27.5	2.4	64.4
Other São Paulo state (Dept+Arr)	Split	35.10%	55.80%	9.10%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	7.4	12	2	21.4
Connections	Split	48.90%	46.10%	5.00%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	21	19.8	2.1	56
Total	Split	48.9%	16,7%	50%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	63	59.4	6.4	128.8

Table 15: Demand for São Paulo Area airports in 2030 in a scenario with high-speed train availability, considering the neutral baseline

Zone		VCP	GRU	CGH	Total
São Paulo and Campinas Metro (Dept+Arr)	Split	70.80%	26.90%	2.30%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	59.5	22.6	1.9	72.7
Other São Paulo state (Dept+Arr)	Split	35.10%	55.80%	9.10%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	9.8	15.6	2.5	28
Connections	Split	61.90%	34.20%	4.00%	100%

	Passengers (millions)	34.7	19.1	2.2	48.4
Total	Split	61.90%	34,2%	4.00%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	104	57.4	6.7	168.1

Table 16: Demand for São Paulo Area airports in 2030 in a scenario with high-speed train availability, considering the conservative baseline

Zone		VCP	GRU	CGH	Total
São Paulo and Campinas Metro (Dept+Arr)	Split	70.80%	26.90%	2.30%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	45.6	17.3	1.5	64.4
Other São Paulo state (Dept+Arr)	Split	35.10%	55.80%	9.10%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	7.4	12	2	21.4
Connections	Split	61.90%	34.20%	4.00%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	26.6	14.7	1.7	42.9
Total	Split	61.90%	34,2%	4.00%	100%
	Passengers (millions)	79.6	44	5.1	128.8